

Retain Your Rights!

NATIONAL POLICYMAKERS 4 steps to implement a national rights retention policy

CHECKLIST

STEP 1 GET INFORMED

- ✓ **GAIN A REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL OVERVIEW:** Get informed on the rights retention and open licensing policies and practices both within your country and internationally amongst your publishers, funders and RPOs. Understand the trends, opportunities, and challenges. Is this being discussed on a national level? Who are your key experts in this field?
- ✓ **CONSULT WITH LEGAL:** Consult with copyright legal advisors to see how publishing rights are managed in your country.
- ✓ **LEARN FROM OTHERS:** Connect with peers to gather insights about other country experiences, good practices, and challenges outside your region that relate to your national context. Consider initiating or joining a forum for idea exchange.
- ✓ **REVIEW AND SIMPLIFY:** Explore whether any centralised or coordinated guidance is provided to academics on copyright and licensing in your country, ensuring consistency with standardised terms. Consider encouraging or funding this idea if it does not yet exist.

STEP 2 DRAFT YOUR POLICY

- ✓ **DRAFT:** Draft a targeted policy that aligns with the OA goals and vision of your country and other related policies. Build on good practices and existing policies where valid, and involve representatives of key stakeholders in its development
- ✓ **CO-CREATE:** Hold consultations, workshops, and public hearings to gather diverse perspectives from key stakeholders. Consult them to make your case, to hear their concerns, and then fine-tune your proposal policy.
- ✓ **STANDARDISE YOUR LANGUAGE:** Strive to develop national or regional guidance that adopts consistent language around copyright and licensing terms, in your national language. Make an effort to translate your policies into English to be able to exchange experiences and suggestions with colleagues internationally.

STEP 3 SPREAD THE WORD & IMPLEMENT

- ✓ **ROLL OUT STRATEGY:** Once the policy is finalised, design a rollout plan detailing how and when the policy will be introduced and who will implement it.
- ✓ **SPREAD THE WORD:** Develop a communication strategy to inform all stakeholders about the new policy, its benefits, and how it affects them.
- ✓ **SET UP SUPPORT SYSTEMS:** Encourage the establishment of, or point to existing support services to assist researchers with their practical questions, be they ethical, rights-based, or technological.

STEP 4 MONITOR AND KEEP TABS ON PROGRESS

- ✓ **SEEK FEEDBACK:** Set up mechanisms to gather feedback from key stakeholders on the policy's impact and challenges faced.
- ✓ **REVIEW PERIODICALLY:** Regularly review and update the policy based on evolving needs, feedback, and changes in the broader academic and publishing ecosystem.
- ✓ **MONITOR COMPLIANCE:** Set up processes to easily monitor policy compliance and consider how to incentivise good practice.